

METHODOLOGY OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF GENETICS

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information about the methodology of using interactive methods in teaching genetics. In particular, the features of teaching genetics that are important for teachers today, modernization of the organization of the educational process of professors and teachers working in higher education institutions, pedagogical work in higher education institutions modernization of the organization of the educational process of professors and teachers, the use of passive methods, active methods, and interactive methods in teaching genetics.

Key words: passive method, active method, interactive method, modernization, adaptive test bank, genetics

The important characteristics for teachers today are to have in-depth knowledge and skills in their specialty and are full of young people who are hungry for knowledge. It will not be enough to provide a large amount of knowledge to the social humanitarian audience. According to the results of many scientific researches conducted in this regard, one of the most effective ways of imparting knowledge is the use of new approaches and interactive approaches to teaching students. In simple words, only when students are actively involved in the learning process will they easily perceive, understand and remember the given materials. Based on this, today the main methodological innovations require the use of interactive teaching methods.

Modernization of the organization of the educational process of professors and teachers engaged in pedagogic activities in higher education institutions, educational-methodical complex, electronic textbooks, non-standard adaptive test bank, training courses by creating a syllabus for activating the cognitive activity of students, developing and updating methodological knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary to achieve educational efficiency, raising them to the level of state requirements and world education standards is one of the main issues of the reform period . Updating the content of the higher education system of the Republic of

Uzbekistan, modernizing the organization of the educational process of professors and teachers working in this educational system in an era of globalization of information, methodological knowledge on the application of innovative technologies to this process, updating skills and qualifications is considered one of the urgent problems of today.

In medical universities, it is determined that the main goal is to teach the science of medical biology and general genetics, based on innovative technologies that meet the requirements of the time, and to teach the design of technological maps. By mastering the module, students will have professional competence to learn, practice and evaluate the design and planning of pedagogical activities.

Passive method, Active method, Interactive method.

Subject-object, that is, the teacher speaks and explains, the student listens, answers when asked. Subject - subject The teacher directs. (Based on the given information) Subject-subject relationship. The teacher organizes, manages. According to the given questions and assignments, the students work together and independently, summarize, explain and defend their opinions. It works together. Interests increase. According to their application in the educational process, interactive methods have several advantages and disadvantages. To eliminate these shortcomings, a number of suggestions and recommendations must be developed. Including:

- The most important thing is for the teacher to constantly work on himself, to be aware of scientific innovations in his specialty, and to constantly improve his professional skills;
- Application of modern pedagogical and information technologies to the educational system from exhibitions for efficient use of time;
- In order to ensure complete control, it is necessary to use the methods of cooperation technology in small groups of teaching and team teaching, to establish self- and mutual control; If the above-mentioned recommendations are used to eliminate the shortcomings in the use of interactive methods, the effectiveness of genetics education will increase, and it will play an important role in the acquisition of biological knowledge by the young generation and their development as a perfect person.

The group of practical methods includes the methods of observation, organization and conducting of experiments, methods of performing practical work, which are suitable for recognizing and identifying objects, observing and conducting experiments, explaining the progress of practical work to students, and drawing up a plan for performing practical work. , will consist of methods of monitoring the execution of

practical tasks, analyzing the results of tasks, self-monitoring, practical work, observation and completion of experiments. Problem-based research methods include creating problem situations, creating a chain of problem questions, creating problem tasks and conducting experiments, creating learning hypotheses for solving problem situations, proving learning hypotheses, comparing objects, conducting logical reasoning, learning includes methods of conducting research experiments, describing learning conclusions and generalizations.

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